

Technical and economical assessment of waste heat recovery on a ceramic industry

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ABSTRACT: Waste heat recovery is key for the improvement of several industrial sectors. It has the potential to be used as an energy source and, therefore, to reduce the current industrial energy consumption. The ceramic industry, in particular, encompasses significant thermal processes (the firing and drying) which generate substantial waste heat. This work studies the potential of waste heat recovery solutions for a ceramic floor tile plant. Direct re-use of hot air streams from kiln cooling zones as kiln combustion air is considered, as well as its use as drying agent and combustion air in dryers. The proposed strategies achieve natural gas savings up to 33% in the plant, reducing fuel consumption by 25-29% in kilns, by 44% in a dryer, and avoiding fuel consumption in the other dryer. Moreover, the payback period of all these strategies has been estimated as 0.12 years, which proves the attractiveness of waste heat recovery.

Keywords: *waste heat; heat recovery; energy efficiency; ceramic industry*

1 INTRODUCTION

The industry sector is accountable for 36% of final energy consumption (IEA, 2017), holding 33% of global GHG emissions. Nearly 70% of industrial energy demand is related to thermal processes, which result in a considerable amount of waste heat. The waste heat is the thermal energy lost in processes once the thermal carrier naturally cools down to the surrounding temperature. Despite its lower exergy, waste heat has the potential to be used as an energy source and thus to reduce current industrial energy consumption. The share of this heat that can be usefully recovered is called the waste heat potential. In EU, the industrial waste heat potential was estimated to be 300 TWh/year, 70 of which held by the non-metallic mineral industries, and with one third being considered as low-temperature (< 200 °C) (Papapetrou et al., 2018). Therefore, industrial waste heat is indeed an attractive topic.

Jouhara et al. (2018) present a comprehensive review of waste heat recovery methods and technologies for industrial processes addressing possible applications for three industrial sectors, namely: the steel and iron, food, and ceramic. The waste heat recovery can be defined as the transferring of heat from a waste heat stream to a process (direct use) or to an energy carrier to be used elsewhere (indirect use). The selected technology for the heat recovery depends on the existing waste heat temperatures and characteristics, and on the existing thermal needs (processes) that can potentially benefit from such recovery. Different heat recovery technologies have been identified and studied in the literature. For instance, conventional burners can be changed and upgraded to regenerative or recuperative burners, which preheat the combustion air (European Commission, 2009; Jouhara et al., 2018). Also, economizers recover heat from exhaust gases (at low-medium temperature) for preheating liquids entering a system. Both sensible heat and latent heat can be recovered in a condensing economizer. Depending on the exhaust gas composition, the use of resistant materials may be required to withstand acid condensate and fouling. Rotary regenerators (as heat wheels) can be used for low-medium temperature applications (mostly in AVAC applications) and may offer a high heat transfer efficiency; however, these may not be fit for high temperature streams due to the risk of physical deformation (Jouhara et al., 2018; Panayiotou et al., 2017). For medium-high temperature streams, alternative heat exchangers may be used. The run around coil is used when two streams must be kept separate and/or are distant from each other. Plate heat exchangers can be applicable for liquids or vapor, working under high temperature and pressure operating limits. Moreover, heat pipes are heat transfer devices with an inner phase change fluid that works as an intermediate heat carrier and provides high thermal conductivity. This technology is currently being studied for its application in industrial waste heat recovery (Delpech et al., 2018; Jouhara et al., 2017). Heat pumps may be used to upgrade low

temperature heat, for instance transfer heat from a lower temperature source to a higher temperature heat sink, requiring a small part of energy (electricity). Furthermore, some technologies can generate electricity from waste heat streams depending on the temperature level: i) thermionic generators for high temperature, ii) thermoelectric generators for medium-high temperature, and iii) piezoelectric materials for low temperature. However, these systems still present low efficiencies and high costs (Jouhara et al., 2018).

The ceramic industry is a non-metallic mineral industry that includes at least two highly energy-intensive thermal processes: the drying and the firing of ceramics. Moreover, some ceramic industries also include the spray-drying process of raw materials in atomizers. Such thermal processes generally are sourced by fossil fuels, such as natural gas, liquefied petroleum gas or fuel oil, whose consumption results in significant emissions to the environment. Additionally, in many ceramic plants, the firing process involves high temperatures (750 - 1200°C) and takes place continuously 24h-a-day. This results in continuous waste heat streams that can represent almost 50% of energy loss (Delpech et al., 2018). Hence, the ceramic industry is a promising sector to consider when assessing opportunities to implement waste heat recovery.

The reference document on best available techniques (BREF) for ceramic manufacturing (European Commission, 2007) and literature on waste heat recovery opportunities (Delpech et al., 2018, 2017) refer that the heat from the cooling zones of tunnel kilns can be recovered to preheat the dryers or to preheat the combustion air. Additionally, depending on the temperatures and heat capacities of exhaust gases, their residual heat can be recovered for other thermal processes using heat exchangers. Furthermore, waste heat could also be used in a Combined Heat and Power generation installation or in an Organic Rankine Cycle to generate heat and electricity for different processes. Though, the economic feasibility of these installations requires careful study, since the capital investment is very high.

Despite the waste heat potential and the significant environmental benefit of waste heat recovery, its implementation depends mainly on the plant operational characteristics, physical constraints, and on attractive economic assessments. Generally, European industries consider an acceptable payback time of 3 years, under which a measure is considered economically viable (Weerdmeester & Tello, 2014).

Generally, industrials disregard the existing waste heat, showing resistance to heat recovery feasibility and its benefits. To allow a greater market uptake of heat recovery strategies, it is important to prove the economic potential of these measures, based on real case-studies' data.

This work presents a study of waste heat recovery strategies for a ceramic floor tile plant. To evaluate heat recovery feasibility, a thermal energy assessment is performed, identifying the existing waste heat streams and heat requirements of the plant. It includes the direct use of waste heat whenever possible, and proposes indirect use through a heat exchanger to produce domestic hot water. Jointly with the energy integration (recovery of waste heat), an economic evaluation to assess its viability is presented. The goal is to identify profitable measures to reduce fossil fuels consumption through waste heat re-use, reducing the associated environmental emissions.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Case study description

The plant under study is a ceramic industry producing floor and wall tiles. The production process includes firstly the mixing of wet raw materials, its casting and pressing. Furthermore, the pressed ceramic tiles are dried in a tunnel dryer (working at 190-200°C). The tiles circulate in counter-current flow with the drier hot air, exiting the dryer with less than 2% of moisture content. After its glazing and decoration, the tiles are fired in a tunnel kiln following a specific gradient temperature, depending on the specific type. The end kiln counts with a cooling zone, which is equipped with cooling air injections that cools down the ceramic tiles, consequently producing a hot air waste stream that is rejected to the surrounding environment. The considered plant includes two production lines, one for special ceramic tiles and other for conventional tiles. Each production line has a tunnel dryer and a tunnel kiln, both running with natural gas. The kilns operate 8760 hours per year, while dryers 6000 hours per year. Figure 1 presents a schematic diagram of above explained process, also named in this work as base case process. Moreover, the base case process streams are further listed in Table 1.

Figure 1. Process flowsheet of the base case process

2.2 Waste heat recovery strategies

Given the huge natural gas consumption of the plant, over 1,500 tons per year, opportunities for waste heat recovery have been identified. In particular, the significant hot waste air rejected (over 21 tons per hour at 123-160 °C) from the cooling zone of the kilns to the surrounding environment. Therefore, its recovery to the process is expected to enhance the plant efficiency. In this sense, wasted hot air streams may be operationally used for two purposes: its direct utilisation as combustion air and its utilisation as drying agent. These strategies are analysed in this study, considering the mass and enthalpy balances, and taking into account the operational requirements of the process. Once the heat recovery and energy savings are determined, an economic assessment is performed to assess this potential improvement.

The ‘available heat’ to be supplied to the drying and firing processes before heat recovery strategies is considered as a constraint condition. The ‘available heat’ is determined by equation (1), in which \dot{M}_{fuel} (kg/h) designates the fuel mass flow rate, LHV (kJ/kg) the fuel low heating value, $\dot{M}_{gas\ stream}$ (kg/h) the mass flow rate of the combustion air, $C_{p,gas\ stream}$ (kJ·°C⁻¹·kg⁻¹) the air heat capacity, T_{out} (°C) the outlet temperature of this gas stream and T_{in} the inlet temperature of this gas stream. The air-to-fuel ratio also constitutes a constraint to the implementation of these strategies, in order to ensure the thermal efficiency of burners remains the same.

$$q_{available} = \dot{M}_{fuel} \times LHV - \dot{M}_{gas\ stream} \times C_{p,gas\ stream} \times (T_{out} - T_{in}) \quad (1)$$

Considering the abovementioned constraints, the potential hot air recovery can be estimated. The global mass and enthalpy balances of dryers and kilns are determined considering the recycling of the air streams and a purging air stream. In the case of the tunnel kilns, the optimized fuel mass flow rate (\dot{M}_{opt}) is determined by equation (2), in which AF designates the air to fuel ratio and $T_{in,recovery}$ (°C) denotes the inlet temperature of the hot air recovered for combustion.

$$\dot{M}_{opt} = \frac{q_{available}}{LHV - C_{p,gas\ stream} \cdot (T_{out} - T_{in,recovery}) \cdot (1 + AF)} \quad (2)$$

$T_{in,recovery}$ is calculated by determining the heat loss on the air ducts that connect the kiln cooling zone and the heated air stream destination. According to equation (3), in which \dot{M}_{air} (kg/h) designates the mass flow rate of the heated air streams and $C_{p,air}$ (kJ·°C⁻¹·kg⁻¹) the air heat capacity, the temperature difference is calculated according to equation (3).

$$T_{in,recovery} - T_{out,cooling\ zone} = \frac{q_{loss}}{\dot{M}_{air} \times C_{p,air}} \quad (3)$$

The heat losses are determined by estimating the convective heat transfer coefficient of the air through empirical correlations, considering the projected length, diameter and thickness of each duct and the estimated velocity of the air.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Waste heat recovery

Following the procedure detailed in section 2.2, hot air streams are integrated within kilns and dryers. Some assumptions are considered to ensure the operability of the process, namely:

- i) heat flow supplied to the tiles and the air-to-fuel ratio, in the combustion zone of kilns and dryers, remain the same than for the base case process;
- ii) temperature of exhaust gases in both kilns and dryers are assumed to remain constant, so as not to modify temperature profile and material requirements.

Considering these assumptions, mass flow and conditions of hot waste air streams are not affected by the integration, since temperature profiles and processed material rates remain constant. Hence, their potential is analysed and a new layout is proposed. Figure 2 shows this proposed layout (integrated process) and Table 1 details the mass flows and temperatures in comparison with the base case process.

Figure 2. Flowsheet of the integrated process.

As shown in the Figure 2, hot waste air from the kilns cooling zone is firstly used as combustion air. The thermal losses in the duct connecting the cooling zone to the combustion air-blower are determined (as presented before in equation 3) to determine the inlet temperature. This temperature is used to achieve the natural gas requirements, considering the abovementioned constraints. As a result, both fuel and combustion air flows are reduced in 29.1% and 24.9% for kilns 1 and 2, respectively. The remaining heat in the air streams is used in upstream dryers in different ways, depending on each one.

The waste heated air from kiln 2 is directly used as a drying agent in dryer 2. The required mass flow is calculated to ensure the heating supply in the dryer, considering the associated heat losses in the duct and the consequent temperature at the inlet of the dryer (157 °C). It has been observed that it has the potential to provide all the required energy in the dryer and, hence, to avoid the use of natural gas in this equipment.

The remaining hot air from kiln 2 is mixed with excess hot air from kiln 1, and then fed as combustion air in dryer 2. However, as the heating potential of this mixed air does not achieve required energy in the dryer 1, it is assumed to be fed as the dryer's combustion air. Furthermore, the higher air temperature at the inlet of the combustor implies a reduction of the natural gas and air flows, which may worsen the humidity removal in the material. Thus, in order to ensure drying capacity, the same exhaust gas mass

flow than the base case process is assumed. This implies also the addition of a direct hot air stream in the dryer. As a result, the natural gas consumption is reduced in 44.2%.

Additionally, an energetic valorisation of the exhaust gases is considered. Although there is no real hot water needs in this plant, its potential production may be attractive in different industrial sectors. The exhaust gases exiting the kilns are mixed and fed into a heat exchanger with the aim of heating water up to 45°C. Thus, a potential for a hot water production of more than 6 tons per hour is calculated, considering the operational time of kilns. Exhaust gases containing acid compounds may produce corrosion problems if condensation occurs in the heat exchanger (Delpech et al., 2017), however the acids concentration in this process is relatively low due to a high quantity of excess air in the kilns (no vestigial quantity of SO_x; 26 mg/Nm³ of NO_x; 4.62 mg/Nm³ F) and these problems may be despised. Moreover, the temperature of the exiting exhaust gases (120 °C) is considered enough to avoid condensation.

Table 1. Mass flows and temperatures of process streams in the base case and in the integrated process.

Base case process			Integrated process		
Stream	Mass flow (kg/h)	T (°C)	Stream	Mass flow (kg/h)	T (°C)
1	15.7	25	1	8.8	25
2	1710.8	25	2	954.8	131
3	1816.8	80	3	1816.8	80
4	108.8	29	4	77.1	29
5	11 858.0	26	5	8405.7	119
6	11 966.0	198	6	8482.9	198
7	2336.3	26	7	2336.3	26
8	12 032.0	26	8	12 032.0	26
9	13 022.9	123	9	13 022.9	123
10	9.6	25	10	0.0	0
11	1041.5	25	11	4564.3	157
12	1084.3	80	12	4564.3	80
13	45.4	29	13	34.1	29
14	3711.0	26	14	2788.1	158
15	3756.0	152	15	2822.3	152
16	2336.3	26	16	2336.3	26
17	13 078.7	32	17	13 078.7	32
18	8934.0	160	18	8934.0	160
			19	853.3	131
			20	1581.6	157
			21	4390.7	131
			22	11 305.1	120
			23	6255.8	15
			24	6255.8	45

3.2 Economic assessment

The economic assessment of the proposed process integration is determined by estimating its investment costs, the potential economic savings and its associate payback period. The economic savings for each measure may be generically calculated by equation (4), in which t_{op} (h/year) designates the annual operational time of the concerned operation, C_{fuel} (€/kJ) the cost of the fuel per unit of energy and $M_{initial}$ (kg/h) the initial fuel mass flow rate. The payback time may be calculated by equation (5), in which C_{Inv} designates the investment cost associated to each measure (which includes installation costs). Maintenance costs associated with new equipment and process configuration are assumed not to be significantly different than existing ones, thus were not considered.

$$Sav = t_{op} \times C_{fuel} \times LHV \times (M_{initial} - M_{opt}) \quad (4)$$

$$PB = \frac{C_{Inv}}{Sav} \quad (5)$$

The implementation of the proposed solution involves an investment cost for the new and required ducting for the heat recovery and the heat exchanger itself and, as described by equation (4), a reduction on the operating costs related to the reduction of the fuel consumption. Hence, economic savings may

compensate investment costs in a short period of time. Table 2 shows the economic evaluation performed, showing an overall pay-back period of 0.12 years. The achieved results show a profitable strategy; however, it is important to note that such payback strongly depends on natural gas price. For the current study the natural gas cost has been considered as 9.33 €/GJ (PORDATA 2018).

Table 2. Economic evaluation of the proposed integrated process.

Technology	Investment Costs (€)	Operation	Natural gas savings (GJ/year)	Savings (€/year)	Payback (year)
Heat exchanger	20 882.49	Kiln 1	13 069	121 934.77	0.12
		Kiln 2	4 658	43 461.38	
Ducts	4 915.21	Dryer 1	2 703	25 214.36	
		Dryer 2	1 962	18 304.85	
TOTAL	25 797.70	TOTAL	22 392	208 915.36	

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a techno-economic assessment of waste heat recovery for a ceramic tiles industry. Considering the base case process involved in the plant under study, potential heat recovery strategies are proposed and evaluated. Results shows that the direct recirculation of heated air from kilns cooling zones to kilns combustors can achieve natural gas reductions of 29% and 25% in kilns 1 and 2, respectively. Moreover, the use of the remaining hot air in dryers can avoid the use of fuel in dryer 2 and reduce the natural gas consumption by 44% in dryer 1. Additionally, an energy valorisation of exhaust gases is identified to potentially produce more than 6 tons per hour of domestic hot water. Overall, proposed recovery strategies reach 33% fuel savings in the studied plant corresponding to a payback period of 0.12 years. Thus, the economic feasibility is proven to be attractive for the current case study, namely a ceramic industry.

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